

THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND MATERNAL HEALTH NEXUS: EVIDENCE FROM LOWER-MIDDLE INCOME COUNTRIES

LUCY BOLAJI BAMISILE

*Department of Economics, Afe Babalola University Ado-Ekiti (ABUAD)
Lucyb0807@yahoo.com+2347030493570*

BOSEDE OLANIKE AWOYEMI

*Department of Economics, Afe Babalola University Ado-Ekiti (ABUAD)
nikeawoyemi@abuad.edu.ng +2348030776250 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6391-2443> (Corresponding author)**

SAMUEL ADEREMI IGBATAYO

*Department of Economics, Afe Babalola University Ado-Ekiti (ABUAD)
s.igbatayo@abuad.edu.ng +2348033800373*

ABSTRACT

The effect of economic development on maternal health remains insufficiently explored in lower-middle-income countries despite persistent high maternal mortality rates in these regions. While economic growth is often expected to improve health outcomes through improved healthcare access, infrastructure development, and higher living standards, empirical evidence on this relationship remains limited. Therefore, this study examined the effect of economic development on maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries (LMICs). The study utilized panel data from 51 LMICs, covering the period from 2000 to 2024. Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) and Driscoll-Kraay estimation techniques were employed to ensure robust estimation in the presence of heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, and cross-sectional dependence. The results revealed that economic development has a consistently negative and highly significant effect on maternal mortality across lower-middle-income countries. The study concludes that economic development plays a crucial role in improving maternal health outcomes. Consequently, governments should promote sustained and inclusive economic growth by encouraging productive investment, strengthening healthcare financing, improving social infrastructure, and implementing policies that expand access to quality maternal healthcare services to reduce maternal mortality.

Keywords: *Economic development, maternal mortality, maternal health, Health outcomes, Lower-middle-income countries, Panel Data, GDP per capita, Healthcare access*

JEL Codes: O11, I12, I18

1. INTRODUCTION

Lower-middle-income countries (LMICs), classified by the World Bank, are economies with gross national income (GNI) per capita between \$1,146 and \$4,465 (Metreau & Eapen, 2024). These countries occupy a critical transitional phase in global development and include nations such as Nigeria, India, Bangladesh, Vietnam, and Kenya. Although many LMICs have experienced moderate economic growth and structural transformation, development outcomes remain uneven. Economic progress in these countries has not consistently translated into improved social welfare due to persistent poverty, weak institutional systems, and unequal access to essential services such as healthcare and education. Consequently, maternal health outcomes remain a major public health concern in many LMICs, reflecting persistent structural inequalities in access to quality healthcare services (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021).

Central to development discourse is the role of economic development as a structural determinant of population health outcomes. Economic development is a multidimensional process involving improvements in income levels, infrastructure development, industrialization, and overall living standards (Todaro and Smith, 2020). Economic expansion enhances government fiscal capacity to invest in healthcare infrastructure, medical technologies, and human capital development, thereby improving maternal healthcare delivery and accessibility. Empirical evidence also suggests that increased public health expenditure and economic resources contribute to improved health outcomes and higher life expectancy by strengthening healthcare systems and expanding access to medical services (Joseph & Agada, 2024). However, the relationship between economic development and health outcomes remains complex, as economic growth does not automatically translate into equitable improvements in population health. In many lower-middle-income countries, economic gains have been accompanied by widening disparities in healthcare access between urban and rural populations, limiting the inclusive benefits of growth (Souza et al, 2024).

Maternal health refers to the physical and mental well-being of women during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period, supported by access to quality healthcare services, education, and social protection systems (WHO, 2023; Johnson and Agyemang, 2020). Recent evidence also indicates that maternal healthcare services such as antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and postnatal care play a crucial role in reducing maternal mortality and improving pregnancy outcomes, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where healthcare systems remain fragile (Baten et al., 2025). Maternal healthcare encompasses a continuum of services, including antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and postnatal care, which are essential for reducing maternal morbidity, hemorrhage, infections, and pregnancy-related complications. Despite global improvements in maternal healthcare interventions, maternal mortality remains disproportionately high in lower-middle-income countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia (WHO, 2021). These disparities are largely driven by limited healthcare infrastructure, shortages of skilled healthcare professionals, and socio-cultural barriers that restrict women's access to essential maternal health services. In addition, low educational attainment reduces awareness of maternal health risks and limits healthcare-seeking behavior, while gender inequality restricts women's autonomy in making reproductive and healthcare decisions (Rahman et al., 2024). These socio-economic constraints collectively reinforce maternal health vulnerabilities and contribute to persistent maternal mortality differentials across population groups.

Despite increasing empirical attention to maternal health determinants, several research gaps remain. First, limited studies have simultaneously examined the nexus among economic development and maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries. Second, many cross-country studies have failed to account for cross-sectional dependence, which may bias empirical estimates in panel data analysis. To address these gaps, this study examines the direct effects of economic development and socio-economic disparity on maternal health outcomes in LMICs using estimation techniques that correct for cross-sectional dependence. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the literature review, Section 3 describes the methodology, Section 4 presents empirical results and discussion, while Section 5 provides conclusions and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The global burden of maternal mortality continues to reflect disparities in economic and social development, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where access to quality healthcare remains limited. Global health systems emphasize that maternal health outcomes depend on a combination of medical care, social protection, and economic opportunities that

support women's well-being during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period. Maternal health services include antenatal care (ANC), skilled birth attendance, and postnatal care, which are essential for monitoring maternal and fetal health, preventing complications such as infections and hemorrhage, and reducing maternal mortality and morbidity risks (WHO, 2021; Amu et al., 2023). Studies further show that continuity of maternal healthcare services across pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period can significantly reduce the risk of maternal and neonatal mortality by improving early detection and management of pregnancy-related complications (Baten et al., 2025). Economic development is therefore central to maternal health discourse because it represents the process of improving economic, social, and political well-being through better living standards, increased income opportunities, and improved human capabilities (Todaro and Smith, 2020). Countries with higher levels of economic development and higher GDP per capita generally record lower maternal mortality rates due to stronger health systems and greater investment in healthcare infrastructure. Similar findings have been reported in developing economies where improvements in health spending and economic conditions significantly enhance population health outcomes and life expectancy (Habib, Awolaja, & Aworinde, 2024). For example, maternal mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa remains extremely high, with approximately 545 deaths per 100,000 live births recorded in 2020, accounting for about 70% of global maternal deaths, compared with much lower rates in high-income regions such as Europe, North America, Australia, and New Zealand (WHO, 2023). These disparities highlight how differences in economic development, healthcare access, education, and social welfare systems influence maternal health outcomes across regions.

In lower-middle-income countries (LMICs), economic development is essential for improving living standards through increased employment opportunities, higher incomes, expanded access to healthcare services, and the adoption of modern technologies (UNDP, 2020). Economic development in these countries extends beyond GDP growth to emphasize inclusive development, where economic gains are shared across all segments of society to improve overall quality of life and human capabilities (Kar, 2023). However, many LMICs continue to face structural development challenges, including weak health systems, limited infrastructure, political instability, and restricted access to quality education, which constrain the effectiveness of economic growth in improving welfare outcomes (Sarikhani et al., 2024). Evidence from West African economies further shows that variations in income levels and economic structures significantly influence health outcomes, including neonatal and maternal mortality indicators (Momoh, 2022). These development challenges are closely linked to persistent socio-economic disparities, which significantly influence maternal health outcomes. Socio-economic inequalities such as income gaps, gender discrimination, low educational attainment, and inadequate healthcare infrastructure limit women's access to essential maternal health services, including antenatal care and skilled birth attendance (UNFPA, 2021). These inequalities are further reinforced by poverty, poor living conditions, and limited decision-making autonomy for women, increasing vulnerability to maternal complications (WHO, 2020; WHO, 2023). Therefore, addressing maternal health disparities in LMICs requires policies that promote inclusive economic development, strengthen healthcare infrastructure, and expand educational and social opportunities for women.

Empirical literature on maternal health has increasingly examined the role of economic development and socio-economic conditions in shaping maternal health outcomes across countries. For instance, Tolossa et al. (2024) reported that maternal healthcare service utilization in Sub-Saharan Africa has improved since the introduction of the Sustainable Development Goals, although significant regional disparities in access to maternal health services still persist. Supporting this argument, Ezenduka, Ojonugwa, Ebeh, and Adegboyega

(2025) found that household health expenditure plays an important role in determining health outcomes in Nigeria, highlighting the importance of financial capacity in accessing healthcare services. Generally, studies suggest that economic development improves maternal health through increased healthcare investment, improved living standards, and expanded access to education and healthcare services. For instance, Yeboah et al. (2025) conducted a systematic review of the effects of economic growth and recession on maternal and child health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1,167 studies identified, 18 met the inclusion criteria covering 2000-2022. The study found that economic growth significantly reduces maternal deaths, child mortality, and undernutrition. However, the study also noted inconsistent evidence, emphasizing that economic growth alone is insufficient without complementary factors such as female education, good governance, and equitable healthcare coverage. Health financing mechanisms have also been identified as important channels through which economic development influences maternal health. Makate and Mahonye (2024) evaluated the effectiveness of results-based financing (RBF) programs in reducing maternal health inequalities in Zimbabwe using an extended two-way fixed effects model applied to demographic and health survey data from 1999 to 2015. The study found significant disparities in maternal healthcare utilization, particularly in family planning, prenatal care, and delivery services. However, RBF programs improved healthcare access among women in lower socio-economic groups, suggesting that targeted financing programs can enhance equity in maternal healthcare delivery. Similarly, Boundioa and Thiombiano (2024) examined public health expenditure and maternal mortality in West African Economic and Monetary Union countries using World Bank panel data from 1996 to 2018. The study employed a two-stage least squares estimation technique and found that public health expenditure was negatively associated with maternal mortality, while private health expenditure showed a positive relationship with maternal mortality.

At the country level, empirical evidence from Nigeria also highlights the importance of macroeconomic conditions for maternal health outcomes. Adegoke et al. (2022) examined macroeconomic determinants of maternal, neonatal, and child mortality using an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model covering 1995–2020. The study found that unemployment positively influenced poor health outcomes, while gross fixed capital formation, household consumption, and health expenditure were negatively associated with mortality rates. Forecast results indicated that Nigeria would need significant increases in health expenditure and capital investment, alongside reductions in unemployment, to achieve Sustainable Development Goal targets by 2030. In addition, Adejorin et al. (2024) analyzed maternal healthcare utilization among rural Nigerian women using data from the 2018 National Demographic and Health Survey. The study applied ordered logit, fuzzy set analysis, and multiple correspondence analysis and found moderate utilization of maternal healthcare services, with better well-being outcomes among women who accessed formal healthcare facilities. Beyond macroeconomic and health system factors, socio-economic determinants remain critical drivers of maternal health outcomes. do Socorro Candeira Costa and dos Santos (2021) examined maternal mortality and socio-economic indicators across Brazilian regions using regression analysis. The study found that maternal mortality was strongly influenced by per capita income, with inverse relationships between maternal mortality, human development index, and income levels. Similarly, Hamal et al. (2020) conducted a scoping review of social determinants of maternal health in India and found that structural factors such as economic status, education, gender norms, and cultural practices significantly influence maternal healthcare utilization. Intermediate determinants such as maternal age, place of residence, and exposure to health information also affected maternal health outcomes.

Overall, empirical evidence suggests that maternal health outcomes are strongly influenced by economic conditions, particularly the level of economic development. Economic development improves maternal health outcomes by enhancing access to quality healthcare services, strengthening health infrastructure, increasing household incomes, and improving living standards. However, most existing studies have examined the relationship between economic development and maternal health using different methodological approaches, with limited evidence on the direct effect of economic development on maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries. In addition, few studies have examined this relationship while accounting for cross-sectional dependence in panel data analysis. This study therefore contributes to the literature by examining the effect of economic development on maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries using robust panel estimation techniques.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The Social Determinants of Health (SDH) theory provides a useful framework for explaining the relationship between economic development and maternal health outcomes. The theory emphasizes that health outcomes are not determined solely by biological or genetic factors; rather, they are largely shaped by broader socio-economic conditions such as income levels, employment opportunities, education, and living standards (Marmot, 2005; WHO, 2023). Within this context, economic development plays a critical role in improving maternal health by enhancing household income, strengthening healthcare systems, and expanding access to essential health services during pregnancy and childbirth (Solar & Irwin, 2010). The SDH framework further recognizes that disparities in economic development across countries and regions create unequal conditions that influence women’s ability to access quality maternal healthcare services. In economies with low levels of development, limited financial resources, inadequate health infrastructure, and poor service delivery often restrict access to antenatal care, skilled birth attendance, and postnatal services. Additionally, economic progress contributes to improvements in living conditions, sanitation, and access to clean water, which are essential for reducing maternal morbidity and mortality (Victora et al., 2003). Therefore, the SDH framework underscores the importance of economic development as a key determinant of improved maternal health outcomes.

3.2 Model specification

The model specified maternal health measured by maternal mortality ratio as function of economic development, with public health expenditure and population growth rate as control variables.

$$LMMR_{it} = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 LGDPC_{it} + \gamma_2 HEX_GDP_{it} + \gamma_3 PGR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Table 1: Variables Description/Masurement, and a priori Expectation

Variables	Description and measurement	A-priori sign
<i>MMR</i>	<i>Maternal Health-Maternal Mortality Ratio</i>	NA
<i>GDP</i>	<i>GDP per capita</i>	-
<i>HEX_GDP</i>	<i>Public health expenditure as percentage of GDP</i>	+
<i>PGR</i>	<i>Population growth rate in percentage</i>	+

Source: Authors’ Compilation (2026)

NA mean not applicable

3.3 Scope, Data source and Estimation Techniques

This study utilized panel data for 51 lower-middle-income countries, covering the period from 2000 to 2024. The countries included in the analysis are Angola, Bangladesh, Benin, Bhutan, Bolivia, Cabo Verde, Cambodia, Cameroon, Comoros, Congo Republic, Côte d'Ivoire, Djibouti, Egypt, Eswatini, Ghana, Guinea, Haiti, Honduras, India, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyz Republic, Lao PDR, Lebanon, Lesotho, Malaysia, Mauritania, Morocco, Myanmar, Nepal, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Pakistan, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Samoa, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, Tanzania, Timor-Leste, Tunisia, Uzbekistan, Vanuatu, Vietnam, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. The data used in the study were obtained from secondary sources, primarily the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) and the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS), which provide reliable cross-country data on key socio-economic and health indicators. For the empirical analysis, the study employed Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) and Driscoll-Kraay estimation techniques to ensure robust and reliable results. The PCSE approach, developed by Beck and Katz (1995), corrects for common econometric problems in panel data such as heteroskedasticity, contemporaneous correlation across countries, and serial correlation within panels, thereby improving the reliability of statistical inference. The Driscoll-Kraay estimator was also applied to account for cross-sectional dependence, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation. Furthermore, the study adopted the four-step mediation framework of Baron and Kenny (1986) to examine the mediating role of economic development in the relationship between socio-economic disparity and maternal health. To ensure the robustness of the mediation results, the Sobel test was also conducted to statistically verify the significance of the indirect effect of socio-economic disparity on maternal health through economic development.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Economic Development and Maternal Health

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 provide a detailed overview of the distributional characteristics of key economic and health-related variables in lower-middle-income countries. The average maternal mortality ratio (MMR) is 248.92 deaths per 100,000 live births, with a relatively high standard deviation of 232.26, indicating considerable variation in maternal health outcomes across countries. The distribution is positively skewed (1.60) and leptokurtic (6.17), suggesting that while most countries record moderate MMR levels, a few experience exceptionally high rates. The average GDP per capita (GDPC) stands at \$2,773.13, with a large standard deviation of \$5,128.83, reflecting considerable income disparities among the sampled countries. These results highlight the persistent economic heterogeneity within this income group. Regarding public health expenditure (HEX_GDP), the mean share of GDP devoted to public health is 5.39%, with a standard deviation of 13.54, revealing significant cross-country variation. The population growth rate (PGR) averages 1.85%, with a standard deviation of 1.09, indicating modest variation across countries. In summary, the descriptive statistics reveal pervasive non-normality across all variables, characterized by strong skewness and high kurtosis. These findings indicate substantial heterogeneity in economic development and maternal health indicators among lower-middle-income countries. To address these distributional imbalances and ensure robust econometric estimation, logarithmic transformation and other normalization techniques were applied in subsequent analyses to stabilize variance and mitigate the influence of extreme observations.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Economic Development and Maternal Health

	MMR	HEX_GDP	GDPC	PGR
Mean	248.92	5.39	2773.13	1.85
Median	183.00	4.43	1578.64	1.80
Maximum	1387.00	343.00	54949.62	9.99
Minimum	2.00	1.51	136.93	-11.36
Std. Dev.	232.26	13.54	5128.83	1.09
Skewness	1.60	24.34	6.62	-0.24
Kurtosis	6.17	606.91	53.79	28.42
Jarque-Bera	107.04	195.00	146.9	343.64
Probability	0	0	0.00	0
Observations	1275	1275	1275	1275

Source: Authors' computation based on data from the World Bank WDI (2025)

4.2 Correlation Analysis for Economic Development and Maternal Health

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix showing the relationship between maternal health (LMMR) and key indicators of economic development, including GDP per capita (LGDPC) and public health expenditure (HEX_GDP), with population growth rate (PGR) as a control variable. The results indicate that maternal mortality (LMMR) is strongly and negatively correlated with economic development (LGDPC) ($r = -0.631$), suggesting that higher income levels are associated with lower maternal mortality. In contrast, public health expenditure (HEX_GDP) shows a very weak negative relationship with maternal mortality ($r = -0.029$), while population growth rate (PGR) has a positive correlation with maternal mortality ($r = 0.216$). None of the independent variables are correlated, and correlation coefficients do not exceed the conventional threshold of 0.8 suggested by Gujarati and Porter (2008) and Hair et al. (2009), indicating the absence of serious multicollinearity among the variables. This supports the reliability of regression analysis and ensures that the estimated relationships are not distorted by strong inter-variable dependencies.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix for Economic Development and Maternal Health

	LMMR	HEX_GDP	LGDPC	PGR
LMMR	1.000			
HEX_GDP	-0.029	1.000		
LGDPC	-0.631	0.006	1.000	
PGR	0.216	-0.065	-0.104	1.000

Source: Authors' computation based on data from the World Bank WDI (2025)

4.3 Driscoll-Kraay and PCSE result of the effect of Economic Development on Maternal Health in Lower-Middle-Income Countries

Following series of pre-estimation tests and diagnostics tests, this study employed the Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) and Driscoll-Kraay robust standard errors to address potential cross-sectional dependence and serial correlation among the 51 lower-middle-income countries (LMICs) observed over 25 years. The PCSE approach is particularly suitable when the number of cross-sectional units (N) exceeds the number of time periods (T), as it corrects for heteroskedasticity and contemporaneous correlation across panels, thereby improving the efficiency and reliability of the estimates. In contrast, the Driscoll-Kraay method provides standard errors that are robust to both heteroskedasticity and cross-sectional as well as temporal

dependence, ensuring additional robustness of the results in dynamic panel settings. The results presented in Table 4.23 indicate that the overall model is statistically significant (Wald $\chi^2(3) = 39.53$, $p < 0.001$), implying that the explanatory variables jointly influence maternal health outcomes, as measured by the maternal mortality ratio (LMMR). The coefficient of GDP per capita (LGDP) is negative and highly significant under both estimation methods (PCSE: coef. = -0.432, $p < 0.001$; Driscoll-Kraay: coef. = -0.415, $p < 0.001$). This demonstrates that a 1% increase in GDP per capita leads to an estimated -0.43 reduction in maternal mortality, underscoring the critical role of economic development in improving maternal health through increased access to healthcare services, better nutrition, and improved living conditions.

In contrast, health expenditure as a percentage of GDP (HEX_GDP) shows a negative but statistically insignificant effect on maternal mortality (PCSE: coef. = -0.0023, $p = 0.926$; Driscoll-Kraay: coef. = -0.00016, $p = 0.436$). Similarly, the population growth rate (PGR) has a positive but insignificant association with maternal mortality (PCSE: coef. = 0.0025, $p = 0.850$; Driscoll-Kraay: coef. = 0.0169, $p = 0.205$). These findings suggest that, while economic growth has a direct and measurable impact on maternal health, the influence of health expenditure and demographic dynamics may require a longer time horizon or supportive institutional frameworks to translate into significant improvements, this observation is consistent with previous empirical studies which show that investments in healthcare systems often yield stronger health outcomes over the long term rather than immediate improvements (Joseph & Agada, 2024). The constant term is positive and highly significant under both methods (PCSE: coef. = 8.34, $p < 0.001$; Driscoll-Kraay: coef. = 8.04, $p < 0.001$), indicating the baseline level of maternal mortality when other variables remain constant. The model explains a substantial proportion of the variation in maternal mortality ($R^2 = 0.9532$ under PCSE estimation and 0.4378 under Driscoll-Kraay estimation), demonstrating strong explanatory power and consistency across methods. Overall, the findings confirm that economic development proxied by GDP per capita is a dominant determinant of maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries. However, healthcare spending and population growth do not exhibit statistically significant short-term effects. The robustness of results under both PCSE and Driscoll-Kraay estimations reinforces the conclusion that sustained economic growth, supported by effective public health policies, is essential for achieving lasting reductions in maternal mortality across developing economies.

Table 4: Results on the Effect of Economic Development on Maternal Health in Lower-Middle Income Countries

LMMR	Coef.	PCSEs			Drisc/Kraay			
		Std. Err	z	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err	t	P> t
HEX_GDP	-0.002	0.025	-0.09	0.926	-0.0002	0.0002	-0.79	0.436
LGDP	-0.432	0.069	-6.26	0.000***	-0.415	0.035	-11.83	0.000***
PGR	0.003	0.013	0.19	0.85	0.017	0.013	1.3	0.205
Constant	8.336	0.474	17.58	0.000***	8.042	0.237	33.88	0.000***
Wald chi(3)	39.53							
Prob chi2	0.000				0.000			
No of obs	1,274				1274			
R-squared	0.9532				0.4378			
F(3, 24)					58.08			
No of Obs.	1275				1275			

Source: Authors' computation based on data from the World Bank WDI (2025)

Note: P-value with ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the effect of economic development on maternal health indicates that GDP per capita, as a proxy for economic development, has a consistently negative and highly significant effect on maternal mortality across LMICs. This finding aligns with existing literature suggesting that higher economic development enhances maternal health outcomes by improving access to healthcare services, nutrition, and living conditions (Yeboah et al., 2025; LaBarbera, 2023), similar findings have been reported in recent studies which show that socio-economic factors such as income level, education, and healthcare infrastructure significantly influence maternal mortality patterns across countries (Tolani et al., 2024). In contrast, health expenditure and population growth rate show statistically insignificant effects, suggesting that increases in spending or demographic shifts alone may not translate into immediate improvements in maternal health without effective institutional support and long-term policy interventions (Makate & Mahonye, 2024; Boundioa & Thiombiano, 2024). The high findings reinforce the conclusion that sustained economic growth is the most critical driver of maternal health improvements, corroborating studies emphasizing the role of household income, women's autonomy, and broader socio-economic conditions in shaping maternal healthcare access and utilization (Adjoorin et al., 2024; Ifelunini et al., 2022). The results resonate with evidence from other LMIC contexts, highlighting that while targeted health interventions are important, structural economic development remains essential for long-term reductions in maternal mortality (Ngoy & Veiga, 2024). This study's findings underscore that policies aimed at promoting economic growth are vital for improving maternal health outcomes in LMICs, and that relying solely on health expenditure or addressing demographic pressures is insufficient to achieve meaningful progress (Yeboah et al., 2025; Awoyemi et al., 2024; LaBarbera, 2023). The study provides robust evidence that economic development critically shapes maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries. Economic development plays a key role in reducing maternal mortality, both directly by improving access to healthcare and living conditions, and indirectly by partially mediating the impact of socio-economic disparities. While public health expenditure and population growth show limited direct effects, the findings underscore that sustainable improvements in maternal health require integrated strategies that simultaneously reduce socio-economic inequalities and promote inclusive economic growth. Collectively, these results emphasize that addressing structural inequalities alongside fostering economic development is essential for enhancing maternal health and achieving equitable health outcomes across lower-middle-income countries. Additionally, global evidence indicates that maternal mortality remains heavily concentrated in low- and lower-middle-income countries, accounting for more than 90% of maternal deaths worldwide, largely due to limited healthcare access and socio-economic inequalities (WHO, 2025).

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATION

This study concludes that economic development plays a crucial role in improving maternal health outcomes in lower-middle-income countries. Higher GDP per capita significantly reduces maternal mortality, indicating that wealthier economies are better able to provide access to healthcare, nutrition, and improved living conditions that protect maternal health. Although short-term effects of healthcare spending and population growth were not significant, the overall findings highlight that sustained economic growth, coupled with sound public health policies, is fundamental for achieving long-term reductions in maternal mortality in LMICs. Hence, the study recommends that policymakers in lower-middle-income countries prioritize strategies that promote sustained economic growth while simultaneously investing in maternal health infrastructure and services. Efforts should focus on creating an enabling environment where economic gains translate into improved access to quality healthcare, better nutrition, and supportive living conditions for women. Additionally, governments should integrate maternal

health objectives into broader economic development plans, ensuring that growth benefits are equitably distributed and that vulnerable populations receive targeted support to reduce maternal mortality.

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